

ATTITUDES OF SPORTS EMPLOYEES RELATED TO GENDER ROLES

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Abstract:

Gender is an ongoing classification of an individual starting from infancy to adulthood. In the Turkish society, the roles of women and men are clearly distinguished by cultural, tradition, custom, beliefs, educational, income and family norms. It is thought that girls in Turkish society can overcome restrictive over-traditionalist attitudes by doing sports. One of the relatively favorable environments for equality between men and women in social life is the sports environment. It is important that the participation of the athletes, coaches, managers and sports specialists in sport environments as well as men and women whose gender role attitudes are favored by all gender role attitudes of all sports employees, will increase the number of sports people in the society as well as increase the number of physically and psychologically healthy individuals, It is thought. The aim of the study based on this idea is to examine the attitudes of sports employees regarding gender roles. The average age of the survey is 30.45 ± 8.41 and 244 sportsmen working in Antalya. Muğla and Bitlis Youth Services and Sports Provincial Directorate constitute the sportsmen. "Attitude Scale Related to Gender Roles" developed by Zeyneloglu and Terzioğlu (2011) was applied to determine the gender perception of sports employees participating in the survey. In the evaluation of data, SPSS 23.0 statistical package program was used frequency analysis Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro Wilk normality test Mann-Whitney U test Kruskal Wallis test Chi-square test Pearson correlation test statistic was used. As a result, gender role attitudes

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of sports employees were found to be significantly different between gender, education, mother, and father education variables. It is noteworthy that the traditional attitudes of female sports employees and the equality attitudes of male sports employees are high. The low level of gender role in marriage according to the level of education of the mother shows that the employees' mothers have traditional holdings in marriage. The high level of egalitarian gender role attitudes in sports employees according to their educational status indicates that they have a traditionalist position in the egalitarian gender role.

Keywords: gender role, sports, sports employees

1. Introduction

Gender was initially introduced as a term that emphasized social construction, as opposed to “sex” as a biological concept. In time, sex and sexuality have also come to be understood as socially constructed (Lykke, 2010). While the concept of gender expresses extreme cultural and psychological differences from the biological differences between men and women, social roles and responsibilities expected from women and men based on these differences are defined by the concept of gender role. In this context, femininity and masculinity represent the gender roles seen by the society as appropriate for women and men (Koca, 2006). Gender roles are the expression of women and men in social settings. The gender role manifests itself as personality traits and behaviors appropriate to women and men and expresses cultural expectations. Behavior that is thought to be appropriate for a man is called masculine, while behaviors that are considered appropriate for women are called feminine gender roles (Rice, 1996). In the past, the sport was used as an area where men showed their height and test their masculinity. At that time, the acceptance of women as spores could be a threat to the manhood of men. (Hall, 1988). According to Theberge (1993), the high level of body and physical performance in the sports experience makes the sporting environment a strong environment for the construction and validation of gender ideologies. Relationships and discourses between sport, physical performance and masculinity influence the cultures of sports institutions. For this reason, sports institutions are often seen as places that reproduce traditional gender roles and male domination (Claringbould and Knoppers, 2008; Shaw, 2006; Shawve Hoerber, 2003). According to the Global Gender Gap Report by the World Economic Forum, there are four critical inequalities among men and women in 130 countries; Economic participation and economic opportunities, political empowerment, access to education and health (World Economic Forum, 2008). Turkey ranks 123th in the gender gap, while in the area of economic participation and

opportunities it ranks 124th among 130 countries (Koca, 2012). In the past 30 years, the international women's movement has been a pioneer in the intellectual and physical development of women, and the role of women in the family and working life has been redefined. Women who have free time and material resources have participated more in the sport. (Martin et al. 2004) Social norms negatively affect the attitudes and attitudes of women and men towards sports and physical activity. One of the factors that can help to achieve gender equality is ensuring spore participation of women and girls (Koca, Öztürk and Aslan, 2012). The roles of women and men in society are influenced by cultural norms, traditional attitudes, beliefs, education, income, family and environmental factors. One of the environments where excessive traditionalist gender attitudes, which is comparatively provided by equality between men and women in social life, is the sports environment. In short, it is important for sportsmen, coaches, managers, sports specialists in sports environments to ensure that the gender role attitudes of all sports employees are equitable and that women also participate in sports environments as much as men. Thus, it is thought that it is important to increase the number of individuals doing sports in the society, increase the number of physically and psychologically healthy individuals and establish a healthy society.

2. Methods

According to some variables, the average age of the participants is 24.45 ± 8.41 , which is 244 sportsmen working in Antalya, Muğla and Bitlis Youth Services and sports Provincial Directorate. The "Gender Race Attitude Scale" developed by Zeyneloğlu and Terzioğlu (2011) was used to determine the gender perception of sports employees participating in the survey.

The Gender Roles Attitude Scale (TCRSS): The scale aiming to measure gender roles perspective was developed by Zeyneloğlu and Terzioğlu (2011) in the sample of university students. Cronbach α internal consistency coefficients for the subscales of the scale were 0.80 for the female gender role, 0.48 for the gender role in marriage, 0.78 for the gender role in marriage, and 0.72 for the male gender role. The scale consisting of 38 items is a 5-point Likert type measure and the answers range from "Totally agreeing" - "Absolutely not." As a result of this scoring, the highest score that can be taken from the scale is 190 and the lowest score is 38, and the higher scores are equalized for each sub-dimension and the lower scores indicate the traditional tendency (Zeyneloğlu and Terzioğlu 2011). Sub-dimensions of the scale; Equal Gender Role, Female Gender Role, Gender Role in Marriage, Traditional Gender Role, Male Gender Role. The Cronbach α internal consistency coefficient for all the scales was also calculated from this research sample and found to be 0.79.

In the evaluation of the data, SPSS 23.0 statistical package program was used, frequency analysis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro Wilk Normality test were applied. Mann-Whitney U Test, Kruskal Wallis Test, Chi-square Test, Pearson correlation test statistic at significance level (0,05) were used in order to determine the relationship and relationship between variables at the (0,05) significance level between the groups.

3. Results

Table 1: Examination of gender role attitude sub-dimensions according to gender variable

Variables	Gender				t	p
	Man (n:166)		Women (n:78)			
	M	SS	M	SS		
Egalitarian gender role	15,56	± 4,06	15,10	± 4,00	-0,900	,368
Female gender role	15,56	± 4,06	15,10	± 4,00	-0,900	,368
Gender Role in Marriage	9,45	± 4,42	6,76	± 3,57	-4,698	,000*
Traditional Gender Role	16,62	± 5,81	12,52	± 5,82	-4,635	,000*
Male Gender Role	7,94	± 5,26	5,44	± 4,06	-3,651	,000*

p<0.05

As seen in Table 1, gender role, traditional gender role and male gender role in marriage were found to be significantly different according to gender variables (p <0.05). The role of gender in marriage is 9.45 ± 4.42 in males, 6.76 ± 3.57 in females, 12.52 ± 5.82 in traditional gender roles 16.62 ± 5.81 in males, 7.94 ± 5 in males, 26 in women and 5.44 ± 4.06 in women. The gender role in marriage, traditional gender role, and male gender role subscales seem to be lower than the male average of female employees. The fact that the average values of gender role, traditional gender role and male gender role in marriage are low in female sports employees suggests that traditional attitude is dominant in women. It is remarkable that the equality attitude values of male and female sports employees are at the same value. Male sports employees living in a male-dominated society share the same gender role scores as women, indicating that male sports employees are moving away from the traditionalist approach.

Table 2: Examination of gender roles attitude sub-dimensions according to educational status variable

Variables	Educational Status of Sports Employees										t	p
	High school n:24		Vocational School n:17		Bachelor's Degree n:176		Master's Degree n:14		Ph.D. n:8			
	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS		
Egalitarian gender role	3,98	±0,79	3,95	±0,64	4,19	±0,67	4,33	±0,48	4,18	±0,55	8,123	,229*
Female gender role	2,86	±0,63	3,03	±0,56	2,91	±0,48	2,85	±0,31	3,09	±0,39	8,123	,229*
Gender Role in Marriage	2,15	±0,60	2,25	±0,59	2,03	±0,51	2,03	±0,39	2,20	±0,51	11,846	,066*
Traditional Gender Role	3,00	±0,71	3,47	±0,76	2,84	±0,75	2,86	±0,72	3,01	±0,72	13,286	,039*
Male Gender Role	2,18	±0,95	2,50	±0,92	2,14	±0,82	2,35	±0,75	2,00	±0,41	7,201	,303*

p<0.05

As shown in Table 2, there was a significant difference between the education level of sports employees and the gender role of equality, female gender role, marital gender role, traditional gender role and male gender role (p <0.05). It is noteworthy that the values of the egalitarian gender role in all levels of education of sports employees are high. The fact that equal gender roles are higher than their values indicates that sporting employees have a traditional attitude toward the egalitarian gender role.

Table 3: Examination of gender role attitude sub-dimensions according to mother education variable

Variables	Maternal educational status in sports employees										t	p
	Primary School (n:128)		Elementary School (n:56)		High school (n:47)		Vocational School (n:4)		Bachelor's Degree (n:8)			
	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS		
Egalitarian gender role	15,28	±4,32	15,91	±3,74	15,38	±3,69	14,00	±2,82	14,37	±3,99	3,595	,609
Female gender role	15,28	±4,32	15,91	±3,74	15,38	±3,69	14,00	±2,82	14,37	±3,99	3,595	,609
Gender Role in Marriage	8,95	±4,07	9,01	±5,12	7,57	±4,26	9,00	±2,94	5,37	±1,40	12,402	,030*
Traditional Gender	16,75	±5,64	14,78	±6,79	12,48	±5,44	14,50	±3,87	12,00	±6,18	24,857	,000*

Role												
Male												
Gender												
Role	7,47	±5,16	7,51	±4,96	6,24	±5,05	6,75	±2,06	5,00	±3,02	6,973	,223

p<0.05

As shown in Table 3, there was a significant difference between mother education level, marriage gender role and traditional gender role ($p < 0.05$). It is noteworthy that while the mother education level has the lowest gender role in marriage at the undergraduate level (5.37 ± 1.40), the traditional gender role at primary education level has a high value of 16.75 ± 5.64 . The low level of gender role in marriage during all periods of the mother education level indicates that the mothers of sports employees have a traditional hold on marriage.

Table 4: Examination of gender role attitude sub-dimensions according to father education variable

Paternal educational status in sports employees												
Variables	Primary School (n:82)		Elementary School (n:56)		High school (n:65)		Vocational School (n:15)		Bachelor's Degree (n: 25)		t	p
	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS	M	SS		
Egalitarian gender role	15,54	±3,58	15,01	±4,40	15,90	±4,50	17,20	±3,74	13,32	±2,60	14,673	,012*
Female gender role	15,54	±3,58	15,01	±4,40	15,90	±4,50	17,20	±3,74	13,32	±2,60	14,673	,012*
Gender Role in Marriage	9,07	±4,33	8,42	±4,07	8,89	±4,86	8,80	±4,61	6,40	±2,88	8,386	,039*
Traditional Gender Role	16,28	±5,48	15,67	±6,48	14,81	±6,34	15,60	±5,42	12,12	±6,14	11,729	,136
Male Gender Role	7,80	±4,89	6,94	±5,45	6,81	±4,97	8,26	±3,78	5,32	5,04	10,204	,070

p<0.05

As seen in Table 4, there was a significant difference between the father education level and the role of gender inequality, gender role in marriage and gender role inequality ($p < 0.05$). The equitable role of the father in all levels of education of the sports employees and the high average of the role of female gender shows the equitable stance of gender role. When we look at the level of education of the father and the role of gender in

marriage, low average values are remarkable. At all levels of the father education level, we can say that the gender role in marriage has a low average, and that the fathers of sport employees have traditional holdings in marriage.

Table 5: Investigation of gender role attitudes according to the response they gave when asked whether you hear the concept of gender or not

Variables	Did you hear the concept of gender?				t	p
	Yes (n: 186)		No (n: 58)			
	M	SS	M	SS		
Egalitarian gender role	15,37	±3,93	15,53	±4,38	,417	,519
Female gender role	16,37	±3,93	15,53	±4,38	,417	,519
Gender Role in Marriage	8,41	±4,43	9,15	±4,04	2,537	,111
Traditional Gender Role	14,93	±6,35	16,55	±5,13	4,118	,042*
Male Gender Role	7,10	±5,03	7,29	±5,09	,012	,912

As shown in Table 5, according to the response given by the sports employees to the question "Did you hear the concept of gender?", The traditional gender role showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$). In the question "Did you hear the concept of gender?", The high value of the average value ($16,55 \pm 5,13$) in the Traditional Gender Role subscale points to the egalitarian attitude. It is noteworthy that sports employees, who did not hear the concept of gender before, showed a good and equitable attitude to the traditional gender role."

4. Discussions and Results

In the study of attitudes of gender roles of sports employees, gender role, traditional gender role and male gender role in marriage were found to be significantly different according to gender variables. The role of gender in marriage is 9.45 ± 4.42 in males and 6.76 ± 3.57 in females, 12.52 ± 5.82 in traditional gender roles, 16.62 ± 5.81 in males, and 7.94 ± 5.26 in males while it was 5.44 ± 4.06 for women. The gender role in marriage, traditional gender role, and male gender role subscales seem to be lower than the male average of female employees. The fact that the average values of gender role, traditional gender role and male gender role in marriage are low in female sports employees suggest that traditional attitude is dominant in women it is remarkable that the equality attitude values of male and female sports employees are at the same value. Male sports employees living in a male-dominated society share the same gender role scores as women, indicating that male sports employees are moving away from the traditional approach (Table 1). In the study titled "The examination of the correlation between the

tendency of violence and gender roles attitudes among the university students", a significant difference was found between gender, the average monthly income of the family, education level of the mother and attitude points related to gender roles (Çetinkaya, 2013). In a number of studies aimed at determining gender roles in women and men, it has been found that women have more equal roles than men (Burt and Scott, 2002, Khalid and Frieze, 2004, Stewart et al., 2004, Wilde and Diekmann, 2005, Kodan, 2013). In the study of Öngen and Aytaç (2013) examining the attitudes of university students towards gender roles, male students were found to have more traditional attitudes than female students.

It has been found that sports employees have a significant difference according to the level of the educational level such as egalitarian gender role, female gender role, gender role in marriage, traditional gender role, male gender role. It is noteworthy that the values of the egalitarian gender role in all levels of education of sports employees are high. The high value of the equality gender role shows that sports employees have a traditional attitude in the egalitarian gender role (Table 2). In a study of gender roles attitudes of parents in raising their children, the attitudes of participants to education were examined by 40.4% university, 37.2% by high school, gender roles were examined and the highest (33.84%) of the respondents (Erzeybek, 2015) have been identified. A total of 780 males aged 18-65 years participated in the study of males' attitudes towards gender roles in Turkey. The highest average score of males was from the Gender Role (Average: 3.81) and the lowest average was from the Gender Mean: 2,28). It was determined that the gender role attitudes of men participating in this research were an equitable approach and marriage showed a traditional approach with low mean value (Özmete and Yanardağ, 2016). According to the findings of Turkey's Values Atlas created by Esmer (2012), it has been determined that as the level of education in general increases in Turkey, there is also an increase in the equality of discourse among the genders.

Significant differences were found between mother education level and gender role in marriage and traditional gender role ($p < 0.05$). It is noteworthy that while the mother education level has the lowest gender role in marriage at the undergraduate level (5.37 ± 1.40), the traditional gender role at primary education level has a high value of $16,75 \pm 5,64$. The low level of gender role in marriage at all levels of the maternal education level indicates that the sporting mothers' mothers have traditional holdings in marriage (Table 3). Akotia and Anum (2012) examined the traditional and egalitarian gender roles of women and men, taking into account education and age variables, and observed that traditional gender roles differed according to the level of education. It has been found that women have lowered the level of traditional gender role perception to the lower level by educational level. It has been determined that the

perceptions of gender roles of young adults and women are a more modern and egalitarian approach. University students' attitudes towards gender roles were examined according to some variables and it was determined that the level of education of the mother had an effect on gender role attitudes (Shooting 2010). There was a significant difference between the level of father education and the role of gender in Equality Role, Female Gender Role, and marriage. The equitable role of the father in all levels of education of the sports employees and the high average of the role of female gender shows the equitable stance of gender role. When we look at the level of education of the father and the role of gender in marriage, low average values are remarkable. We can say that the father of sports employees has a traditional hold in marriage (Table 4) because all levels of the father education level have low average gender role in marriage. In the study titled "Determining the Gender Role Attitudes of Parents during rising up their children", a significant correlation was found between parental education status and democratic egalitarian attitude (Erzeybek, 2015). The traditional gender role was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) according to the response given by the sports employees to the question "Did you hear the concept of gender?". In the question "Did you hear the concept of gender?", The high value of the average value ($16,55 \pm 5,13$) in the Traditional Gender Role subscale points to the egalitarian attitude. It is noteworthy that the sports employees exhibit a good and equitable attitude towards the traditional gender role of those who have not heard the gender concept before (Table 5). In the study of the students' attitudes towards gender roles, it was determined that they were changed according to the marital status, class, faculty, family type, education level of mother and brother number, in particular, gender, traditionally or equally. In addition, students are classified as traditional male students, traditional female students, and egalitarian male students (Başcı, 2016). In the study titled Determining the Gender Role Attitudes of Parents during rising up their children, it was observed that the participants who participated in the survey (33.84%) had adopted equal gender role (Erzeybek, 2015) while the findings of their attitudes towards gender roles were discussed. As a result, it was found that sports employees showed significant differences according to gender role attitudes, gender, education, parents education variables. It is noteworthy that the traditional attitudes of female sports employees and the equality attitudes of male sports employees are high. The low level of gender role in marriage according to the level of education of the mother shows that the employees' mothers have traditional holdings in marriage. The high level of egalitarian gender role attitudes in sports employees according to their educational status indicates that they have a traditionalist position in the egalitarian gender role. It is suggested that employees in sports fields should be educated about gender issues to raise awareness and spread the desired egalitarian behavior in every part of the society.

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